

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

Journal Full Title: [Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences](#)

Journal NLM Abbreviation: J Biomed Res Environ Sci

Journal Website Link: <https://www.jelsciences.com>

Journal ISSN: 2766-2276

Category: Multidisciplinary

Subject Areas: Medicine Group, Biology Group, General, Environmental Sciences

Topics Summation: 130

Issue Regularity: [Monthly](#)

Review Process: [Double Blind](#)

Time to Publication: 21 Days

Indexing catalog: [Visit here](#)

Publication fee catalog: [Visit here](#)

DOI: 10.37871 ([CrossRef](#))

Plagiarism detection software: [iThenticate](#)

Managing entity: USA

Language: English

Research work collecting capability: Worldwide

Organized by: [SciRes Literature LLC](#)

License: Open Access by Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. Based on a work at SciRes Literature LLC.

Manuscript should be submitted in Word Document (.doc or .docx) through

Online Submission

form or can be mailed to support@jelsciences.com

**IndexCopernicus
ICV 2020:
53.77**

 Vision: Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences main aim is to enhance the importance of science and technology to the scientific community and also to provide an equal opportunity to seek and share ideas to all our researchers and scientists without any barriers to develop their career and helping in their development of discovering the world.

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Affecting the Pedagogy of Death by COVID-19

Anabel Ramos-Pla*

Department of Pedagogy, Faculty of Education, Psychology and Social Work, University of Lleida, 25001 Lleida, Spain

Introduction

Death is one of the most prevailing social and pedagogical taboos in our western society [1-6]. Taking this context into account, we are committed to the application of a preventive pedagogy on death -understood as the teaching of death prior to the tragic event- as a transversal and radical axis in schools in order to promote its normalisation [7-10], to promote the comprehensive education of students and avoid possible pathological grief [11-14].

As education professionals, we often forget that pedagogy must be based on authenticity and loss, and death enables the rediscovery of values such as serenity, patience, humility, silence, etc. The opportunities offered by the school space to educate for finitude must be taken into account; education professionals can offer approaches and strategies to students to become aware of death in order to find a unique meaning in life.

Children are not preparing for life, they are already living it [15], and for them, as part of human existence, encountering the death of a loved one is inevitable. Moreover, the ability to understand death, to go through the stages of mourning and to continue living effectively is essential to ensure the well-being of creatures. In other words, we must accept that death is a reality of every living being, and we must therefore carry out a pedagogy of human finitude. In our role as education professionals, we must bear in mind that there is a didactic bifurcation in the teaching and pedagogical approach to death [16]:

- Prior to a tragic event. This is developed permanently through cross-cutting themes or areas of knowledge in the curriculum
- Post or palliative. However, both perceptions have continuity within the educational process on death. We firmly believe that it is not necessary for a loved one to die in order for its content and all that it entails (social, emotional, biological, etc.) to be taught.

Along these lines, [17] add that death should be anticipated and children should be given answers so that they can be prepared when such events occur. As we have already mentioned, there are other cross-cutting themes, such as recycling, road safety education, peace education, etc., which are taught without any previous tragic event, such as a traffic accident or a war. From our point of view, we believe that teaching the content of death as part of the human life cycle will enable pupils to gradually find meaning in their lives.

For all these reasons, the aim of this study is to analyse the current state of the question of education for death in times of COVID-19.

*Corresponding author

Anabel Ramos-Pla, Department of Pedagogy, Faculty of Education, Psychology and Social Work, University of Lleida, 25001 Lleida, Spain

Tel: +349-737-03374

E-mail: anabel.amos@udl.cat

DOI: 10.37871/jbres1515

Submitted: 14 July 2022

Accepted: 21 July 2022

Published: 23 July 2022

Copyright: © 2022 Ramos-Pla A. Distributed under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0

OPEN ACCESS

Keywords

- > Pedagogy of death
- > Death education
- > Innovation
- > Educational needs
- > Teacher training

GENERAL SCIENCE

EDUCATIONAL SCIENCE

VOLUME: 3 ISSUE: 7 - JULY, 2022

Methodology

The methodology used was qualitative [18,19], in which various In-depth interviews were conducted and analysed. The in-depth interviews consisted mainly of three questions:

- Have you had any training in the pedagogy of death during your apprenticeship as a teacher?
- If yes, what kind of training?
- If no, why do you think this happens, especially in a pandemic situation?

In addition, a case study [20-23] was carried out in Catalonia (Spain) in order to approach a first contextualised reality in relation to the pedagogy of death in the COVID-19 period.

In this case, it was carried out a case study and the sample consisted of 26 interviews:

- Students in the 4th year of the degree in Primary Education at the University of Lleida.
- Teachers working in Primary Education schools in the city of Lleida.

The sample was recruited via institutional e-mail to both students and practising teachers.

The data were analysed using Atlas.ti software. The themes of analysis were:

- Realisation of training in the pedagogy of death.
- Type of training on pedagogy of dying
- Causes of the pedagogical taboo in initial teacher training.

Results

70% of the informants have not undertaken any training in relation to death education, neither in initial nor in continuing education:

"There are not enough educational experiences in training on death education." (MA4).

"During the whole degree course, only one part of a class was devoted to explaining to us that we should be educated in relation to death." (EGEP9).

Discussion

In this context of pandemic and taking into account that there is hardly an educational centre in which there is not a bereaved person, Education for Death is more necessary than ever [24-26]. Not only in the palliative sphere (when the loved one has died and their environment is in the process of mourning), but also in the preventive or previous sphere (working on death from a social and pedagogical normality). The results of this study demonstrate the social and pedagogical taboo in Western society. Although the pandemic situation highlights this research gap, few studies

have been carried out on the subject, as pointed out by [27-29].

Conclusion

It is imperative to address the pedagogy of death in initial teacher training. If future teachers do not become aware of the need to address it in the classroom, it is unlikely that they will deal with it in their professional development.

Recommendations

It is recommended to rethink initial teacher training in order to interrelate as much content as possible from the university career with death.

In addition, both future and current teachers are also encouraged to undertake continuous training on the subject in question.

References

1. Aradilla A. La muerte una pedagogía emocional. *Monitor Educador*. 2004;105:13-16.
2. González I, Herrán A. Introducción metodológica a la muerte y los miedos en Educación Infantil. *Tendencias pedagógicas*. 2010;15(1):124-149.
3. Rodríguez Herrero P, Herrán A, Cortina M. Educar y vivir teniendo en cuenta la muerte. Reflexiones y propuestas. Madrid: Ediciones Pirámide. 2015.
4. Villaceros M, Bermejo JC, Magaña M. Duelos familiares o colectivos. Diseño de una escala de actitudes hacia los niños en procesos de duelo. *Revista de Psicoterapia*. 2016;27(104):167-179.
5. Ramos-Pla A, Gairín J, Camats R. Principios prácticos y funcionales en situaciones de muerte y duelo para profesionales de la Educación. *REICE: Revista Iberoamericana sobre Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación*. 2018;16(1):21-33. doi: 10.15366/reice2018.16.1.002.
6. Ramos-Pla A, Gairín J, Camats R. Percepciones educativas en relación a la pedagogía de la muerte. *Espacios*. 2020;41(4):4-12.
7. Head BA, Smith LC. Use of Contemporary Film as a Medium for Teaching an Online Death and Grief Course. *J Soc Work End Life Palliat Care*. 2016 Jul-Sep;12(3):195-213. doi: 10.1080/15524256.2016.1201564. PMID: 27462949.
8. Gao M, Slaven M. Best practices in children's bereavement. A qualitative analysis of needs and services. *Journal of Pain Management*. 2017; 10(1):199-126.
9. Campillo Ruiz E, Ruiz Arriaza J. Educar para la muerte a través de la didáctica de la literatura. *Publicaciones didácticas*. 2017;82:648-653.
10. Ramos-Pla. Análisis de la situación actual de la pedagogía preventiva sobre la muerte: currículum y formación del profesorado. *ENSAYOS: Revista de la Facultad de Educación de Albacete*. 2020;35(2):221-233. doi: 10.18239/ensayos.v35i2.2358.
11. Fernández Hurtado I. El Joan ha mort. Conte i guia per acompanyar els nens i els adolescents en el dol i la comprensió de la mort. Lleida: Pagès Editors. 2013.
12. Uribe S. Comentarios al trastorno persistente de duelo complicado del DSM-V. *Revista Iberoamericana de Psicotraumatología y Disociación*. 2015;7 (1):1-6.
13. Dodd A, Guerin S, Delaney S, Dodd P. Complicated grief: knowledge, attitudes, skills and training of mental health professionals. A systematic review. *Patient Education and Counseling*. 2017;100 (1):1-35.
14. Ramos-Pla A, Gairín J. Estudio sobre la pedagogía preventiva sobre la muerte: reto y oportunidad. *Espacios*. 2020;41(42):1-14.
15. Kroen W. Cómo ayudar a los niños a afrontar la pérdida de un ser querido. Barcelona: Paidós. 1996.
16. Herrán A, Cortina M. La educación para la muerte como ámbito formativo: más allá del duelo. *Psicooncología: Investigación Y Clínica Biopsicosocial En Oncología*. 2008;5(2-3):409-424
17. Poch C, Herrero O. La muerte y el duelo en el contexto educativo. Reflexiones, testimonios y actividades. Barcelona: Paidós. 2003.
18. McMillan J, Schumacher S. Investigación educativa. Madrid: Pearson Educación SA. 2005.

19. Martínez-Salgado C. El muestreo en investigación cualitativa. Principios básicos y algunas controversias. *Ciència & Saúde Coletiva*. 2012;17(3):613-619.
20. Coller X. Estudio de casos. Madrid: Centro de Investigaciones Sociológicas. 2000.
21. Stake R. Investigación de estudio de casos. Madrid: Morata. 1999.
22. Yin RK. Case Study Research: Design and Methods. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications. 2003.
23. Yacuzzi E. El estudio de caso como metodología de investigación; teoría, mecanismos causales, validación. Argentina: Universidad del CEMA. 2005.
24. Ramos-Pla A, Camats R. Consideraciones generales respecto a la necesidad de practicar una pedagogía sobre la finitud humana en la educación formal: estudio de caso. *Educar*. 2019;55(1):279-290. doi: 10.5565/rev/educar.950.
25. Ramos-Pla A, Selva Pareja L. DOTS-educa: 10 meses, 10 retos. Dykinson. 2020.
26. Ramos-Pla A. Pedagogia de la mort: percepcions i necessitats formatives que té el professorat d'escoles i els aprenents de mestre pel que fa a la pedagogia preventiva sobre la mort [doctoral thesis, Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona]. Repositorio de Tesis Doctorales en Red (TDX). 2018.
27. Ramos-Pla A. ¿Formar al profesorado en pedagogía de la muerte? *Cuadernos de Pedagogía*. 2017;483:82-85.
28. del Arco I, Flores Ò, Ramos-Pla A. Structural model to determine the factors that affect the quality of emergency teaching, according to the perception of the student of the first university courses. *Sustainability*. 2021;13(5):2945. doi: 10.3390/su13052945.
29. Ramos-Pla A, del Arco I, Flores Ò. University Professor Training in Times of COVID-19: Analysis of Training Programs and Perception of Impact on Teaching Practices. *Education Sciences*. 2021;11(11):684. doi: 10.3390/educsci11110684.

How to cite this article: Ramos-Pla A. Affecting the Pedagogy of Death by COVID-19. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci*. 2022 July 23; 3(7): 794-796. doi: 10.37871/jbres1515, Article ID: JBRES1515, Available at: <https://www.jelsciences.com/articles/jbres1515.pdf>